

MAJOR GENERA OF PAPAVERACEAE (POPPY) PLANT FAMILY IN ISRAEL AND PALESTINE. PART III: *GLAUCIUM* (HORNED POPPY)

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ABSTRACT

In the first two of this series of triad articles, we reviewed the genera of *Fumaria* and *Papaver*, included in the Papaveraceae plant family of Israel and Palestine, the reviewed region, RR. In this article, we review the third major genus of this family in the RR, *Glaucium*. The species of this genus in the RR were significantly studied but the number of their reported medicinal properties-activities is relatively limited compared with *Fumaria* and *Papaver*. Expectedly, the chemical compositions of these species comprise active alkaloids and other compounds, yet some of these compositions are only partially known. Interestingly, the traditional uses of these species are well known and documented. So these traditional uses, as well as modern research findings, will be presented in two separate tables. Structures of selected natural products that were isolated from these plants are shown after these tables, followed by a

thorough discussion. Finally, conclusions and recommendations for future research will be made.

KEYWORDS: Papaveraceae, *Glaucium*, *Glaucium flavum*, *Glaucium grandiflorum*, Alkaloids, Ethnomedicine, Chemical composition, Anticancer, Anti-inflammatory, Neuroprotective.

Abbreviations: ABTS 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid), ahc and her/his colleagues, AChE acetylcholine esterase, β CBM β -Carotene bleaching method, BHT butylhydroxytoluene, BuChE butyrylcholine esterase, CNS central nervous system, COX cyclooxygenase, CUPRAC cupric reducing antioxidant capacity, DCM dichloromethane,

DPPH 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, EDTA ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, FRAP ferric reducing activity power, GCC general chemical composition, GC-MS gas chromatography mass spectrometry, GPx glutathione peroxidase, HPLC high performance liquid chromatography, IL-(number) interleukin, LPS lipopolysaccharide, MENA Middle East and North Africa, NI not indicated, NPs nanoparticles, PE petroleum ether, ROS reactive oxygen species, RR reviewed region, SOD superoxide dismutase, TAC total antioxidant capacity, TBARS thiobarbituric acid reactive substances, TFC total flavonoid content, TPC total phenolic content.

1. INTRODUCTION

The *Glaucium* genus as part of the Papaveraceae (Poppy, خشخاشية, פרגיים, English, Arabic, Hebrew, respectively) plant family, has a common name of Horned-Poppy, ממיטה, פרגה in these languages. Like the Arabic name of *Fumaria*, شاهترج that emerged from Persian, most scholars agree that the Arabic and Persian names of *Glaucium*, ماميثا, originated from Syriac language.^[1] In rare cases, other scholars like S.A. Oran from Jordan, used Qatra قطرة (means a drop) for *Glaucium arabicum*.^[2]

The total number of species that the genus of *Glaucium* globally comprises is 23-28, and the numbers are notably debated.^[3-5] However, according to the website of “Plants of Israel and Adjacent Areas”, in the RR there are six *Glaucium* species growing wild.^[6] These are: *Glaucium aleppicum*, *G. arabicum*, *G. corniculatum*, *G. flavum*, *G. grandiflorum* and *G. leiocarpum*.

Archaeological and historical studies showed that the plants of *Glaucium* genus were used by humans since ancient times. Several publications reported the presence of *Glaucium* remains in ancient human sites dating around 3200-3400 years before present time, but the *Glaucium* species or its use were not specified: C. Rössner ahc, central Black Sea region, Turkey^[7], J. Valera ahc, Tell Khamis, Syria^[8] and J.M. Marston, Gordion, Turkey.^[9] Unlike the three previous reports, A. Livarda and G. Kotzamani reported the use of unspecified species of *Glaucium* species in Crete, Greece, approximately 3200 before present time, but it was used for medicinal and fuel purposes.^[10] K. Reed ahc, reported that *Glaucium corniculatum* was ritually burnt in churches of Croatia during medieval ages.^[11] A. Torma ahc, found that the same species was used as a cereal in Szigetvár, Hungary, around 1650.^[12]

Unexpectedly, we found only one significant review article about *Glaucium* genus, published by T. Akaberi ahc in 2021.^[13] It is a detailed and comprehensive article (21 pages, 154 references), but it focuses on one (important) aspect of these plants: alkaloids.

2. Ethnobotanical and Ethnomedicinal Uses of *Glaucium* Plants of Israel and Palestine

Ethnobotanical and ethnomedicinal uses of *Glaucium* plants of Israel and Palestine are well documented and published, and we found publications about all six species. Some of these species were published more than others. Geographically, the traditional uses of these plants were (some still) done by many cultures and nations. Summary of these publications is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Ethnobotanical Uses of *Glaucium* Plants of Israel and Palestine.

<i>Glaucium</i> Species	Country; Plant part(s); method(s); use(s); reference
<i>G. aleppicum</i>	Jordan; whole plant, NI, toxic ^[14]
<i>G. arabicum</i>	Egypt; NI, NI, skin and eye infection ^[15,16] Israel; flowers, leaves, stems; NI; eye infection ^[17]
<i>G. corniculatum</i>	Iraq; roots; decoction; sedative, cooling, mild laxative ^[18] Israel; flowers; decoction; eye infection ^[19] Jordan; whole plant, NI, toxic ^[14] Aerial parts; decoction; arthritis ^[20] Aerial parts; warts, antitussive, CNS disturbances, sedative, cooling, mild laxative ^[21] Middle East; NI; NI; (mentions in ancient medicine books) ^[22] Morocco; seeds; snacks ^[23,24] Romania; NI; NI; children diseases ^[25] RR; leaves; decoction (detailed); eye inflammation ^[26] Roots; poultice; cholesterol lowering; acne ^[27] Turkey; flowers; infusion; appeaser, antitussive ^[28] Flowers; infusion; antistress, sedative ^[29]
<i>G. flavum</i>	Iran; seed; powder; laxative ^[30] Italy; NI; NI; ritual child bathing, hematoma ^[31] Morocco; Flowers; decoction; skin diseases ^[32] Romania: aerial parts; infusion; diuretic, antitussive; renal and respiratory disorders ^[33] Turkey; aerial parts; infusion; warts wounds of human/animals ^[34]
<i>G. grandiflorum</i>	Global; NI; NI; hypertension ^[35] Leaves; decoction; hypertension ^[36] Iran; leaves; decoction; hypertension ^[37] NI; NI; diabetes ^[38] Turkey; NI; NI; narcotic, expectorant, insecticide, bradycardia ^[39] Flowers; tea; pertussis ^[40] Flowers; cold drinks ^[41] Aerial parts; NI; NI; NI (just mentioned as medicinal plant) ^[42] Petals; decoration ^[43] Leaves; eaten fresh ^[44]

<i>G. leiocarpum</i>	MENA; aerial parts; NI; anti-infections ^[45] Turkey; branches with leaves; tea; somniferous, antitussive ^[29] Leaves; NI; medicinal plant for humans/animals ^[46] Leaves; poultice (with tobacco); headache ^[47] Flowers, leaves; decoction; diarrhea, headache ^[48] Leaves; cigarettes (smoked) headache ^[49] Fruits; cooked; food ^[50]
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3. Published Medicinal Properties-Activities of *Glaucium* Plants of Israel and Palestine

Compared with other plant genera, the number of medicinal properties-activities of *Glaucium* species of Israel and Palestine is relatively limited. The anticancer activity was notably published and *Glaucium grandiflorum* was published more than each of the other species. A summary of these findings is presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Medicinal Properties-Activities of *Glaucium* Plants of Israel and Palestine.

<i>Glaucium</i> Species	Property-Activity, Method, Results, Reference
<i>G. aleppicum</i>	<p>Whole plant aqueous and 80% aqueous methanolic extracts were analyzed for TPC and tested for antioxidant activity using ABTS and TEAC methods.^[51]</p> <p>Whole plant was defatted with <i>n</i>-hexane then extracted with methanol in guided bioassay for alkaloids. The methanolic extract was tested for acute toxicity (brine shrimp test) and cytotoxicity (against MV3 and colorectal SW480 cell lines). The extract was chromatographed (HPLC) affording five alkaloids: Allocryptopine, Corydine, Isocorydine, Norchelidonine and Protopine (Figure 1).^[52]</p> <p>A follow up of previous study with more efficient chromatographical method, afforded the five alkaloids mentioned above, seven more (Chelerythrine, Corytuberine, Dehydroglaucine, Dihydrochelerythrine, Fumafloirine, Norsanguinarine and Norisocorydine, Figure 1) and unknown compound, C₁₈H₁₄NO₅.^[53]</p> <p>NI plant part(s)^a 80% aqueous methanolic extract had notable lipase inhibition compared with 28 other plants.^[54]</p> <p>Similar study by the same group where aerial parts methanolic extract was analyzed for TPC and tested for xanthine oxidase inhibition was investigated: moderate.^[55]</p> <p>a- In the experimental part of this article, "Plant extraction", it is written that "sample of each ground plant material of the used parts (Table 1)". In table 1 no plant parts (for all 29 plants) are mentioned.</p>
<i>G. arabicum</i>	<p>Aerial parts alkaloid extract (extraction sequence: NH₄OH, DCM, methanol) was chromatographed yielding nine alkaloids and three phytosterols. Two of the alkaloids were new: Araglaucine A and Araglaucine B (Figure 2). In addition, seven known alkaloids that five of them are listed here were isolated (Figure 2, other two are shown in Figure 1): Araglaucine C, <i>N</i>-Methylcanadinium nitrate (compound 1), <i>N</i>-Methylstylophine, 14-Hydroxy-<i>N</i>-methyl canadine, 14-Hydroxy-<i>N</i>-methyl stylophine. Testing all compounds against melanoma (B16 cells) showed that compound 1 was most active.^[56]</p> <p>Whole plant aqueous extract had anticholinergic, antihistaminic and</p>

	<p>antispasmodic activities, tested in smooth muscles of rabbit and guinea pig.^[57]</p> <p>Aerial parts chloroform extract was chromatographed affording Allocryptopine (Figure 1), which had relaxant effect on rat ileum. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[58]</p> <p>Whole plant aqueous extract had relaxant activity on uterine smooth muscles of rat and guinea pig.^[59]</p>
<i>G. corniculatum</i>	<p>Aerial parts were separately extracted with methanol and water. The extracts were analyzed for total alkaloid content, TFC and TPC. The extracts were also tested for AChE inhibition, cytotoxicity (against PC12 cells) and anticancer activity (against HT-29, HeLa cells).^[60]</p> <p>A follow up of previous work where the relationship between AChE inhibition and neuroprotective and antigenotoxic properties of the extracts was studied, using several biochemical parameters.^[61]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanol (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding ten alkaloids Bulbocapnine, Dehydrodicentrine, Dicentrine, Glaucine, N-Methylaurotetanine and O-Methylflavinantine (Figure 3), in addition to Allocryptopine, Corydine, Isocorydine, Protopine.^[62]</p> <p>Aerial parts 90% aqueous methanolic^b extract was fractionized with three solvents and the DCM fraction was chromatographed. Berberine and Dehydroberberine (Figure 3) were isolated with four others (Allocryptopine, Corydine, Glaucine, Protpine), along with eight known phenolics, two of them isolated for the first time from <i>Glaucium</i> and Papaveraceae plants: Quercetin-3-O-glucoside-7-O-rutinoside and Isorhamnetin 3-O-glucoside-7-O-rutinoside.^[63]</p> <p>Aerial parts alkaloid (chloroform) was analyzed affording Talicmidine (Figure 3), in addition to Allocryptopine, Corydine, Glaucine, Isocorydine and Protopine.^[64]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract had enzyme inhibition activity (AChE, BuChE and prolyl oligopeptidase). Analysis of the extract with GC-MS afforded Allocryptopine (52.92%) and Protopine (25.38%) as major components.^[65]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was tested for antioxidant activity (ABTS, CUPRAC, βCBM methods) and enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity. The extract was chromatographed yielding major components Glauciumoline (Figure 3), N-Methyl canadine Glaucine and Protopine.^[66]</p> <p>Aerial parts aqueous and methanolic extracts neuroprotective activity against H₂O₂-induced neuroinflammation in PC12 cells. Effect was measured using IL-6 and IL-10 cytokine levels. The extracts were analyzed (HPLC) affording Rutin and Quercetin as major components, and authors refer the extracts activity to these compounds.^[67]</p> <p>Follow up of previous study with two differences: chloroform extract was also prepared and tested, semi-detailed chemical compositions (some single compounds were identified but most were compound families and functional groups) of the extracts were determined.^[68]</p> <p>b- In the experimental section (Extraction and isolation of compound) it was mistakenly mentioned that plant material was extracted with 90% aqueous ethanol. But the text continues with “the methanolic extract”.</p>
<i>G. flavum</i>	<p>Aerial parts alkaloid (chloroform) was analyzed affording Corunine and</p>

Isoboldine (**Figure 4A**), in addition to Allocryptopine, Chelerythrine, Corydine, Glaucine, Isocorydine, Protopine and Sanguinarine.^[64]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous ethanolic extract was prepared and tested for **antiarthritic** (egg albumin denaturation method), **antihistaminic** (in rat peritoneal mast cells) and **antiobesity** (inhibition of pancreatic lipase) activities. The extract was chromatographed affording Glaucine, Isoboldine, Quercetin-7-O-rutinoside and Rutin, as major active compounds.^[69]

Roots methanolic (alkaloid) extract had **anticancer** activity against MCF10A cells. The extract was analyzed (HPLC) affording Protopine as major component.^[70]

Aerial parts 96% aqueous ethanolic extract had **anticancer** activity against A549 lung carcinoma cells.^[71]

Follow up of previous study: the extract **anticancer** activity was compared to a standard drug, small molecule S14161 (see structure in **Figure 4A**).^[72]

Aerial parts ethanolic extract was tested for **analgesic** (acetic acid-induced writhing method, in rats, 7% acacia gum was reference), **anti-inflammatory** (carrageenan-induced paw edema, diclofenac sodium was reference), **cytotoxic** (against five cancer cell lines), **antimicrobial** (against six bacterial and two fungal strains, with three standard drugs as references) activities. Chromatography of the extract afforded (major alkaloids) Catalane, Oxoglucine, Pontevedrine (**Figure 4A**) and Glaucine.^[73]

Aerial parts were successively extracted with PE, ethyl acetate and 90% aqueous ethanol, and the extracts were analyzed for TFC and TPC and condensed tannins content. The extracts were tested for **anticancer** (against MCF-7 cancer cells) **anti-inflammatory** (LPS-induced in murine macrophage RAW 264.7 cells) and **antioxidant** (DPPH, FRAP, β CBM and TAC methods) activities. The extracts were partially analyzed for chemical compositions affording seven known phenolic compounds.^[74]

Aerial parts and roots methanolic (alkaloid) extracts were prepared and chromatographed (HPLC) yielding Bocconoline, Chelidonine, Magnoflorine, Sanguinarine (**Figure 4A**), in addition to Glaucine, Chelerythrine, and Protopine. The extracts, Bocconoline and Protopine had **anticancer** activity against MDA-MB-231 cells.^[75]

Leaves aqueous extract had **corrosion inhibition** activity against concentrated sulfuric acid solution in steel.^[76]

Decoctions were prepared from fruits, leaves, roots and stems and had **antidiabetic** activity in glucose- or alloxan-induced in rabbits.^[77]

Aerial parts 96% aqueous ethanolic extract had **enzyme enhancing** (aspartate aminotransferase AST, alanine aminotransferase ALT and alkaline phosphatase ALP) and increase of **insulin concentration** in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. Glibenclamide was reference drug.^[78]

Follow up of previous study but in this research, the **functioning of kidney and liver** were improved.^[79]

Another follow up of previous two studies: the **functioning of GPx, SOD and catalase** was investigated.^[80]

Capsules that contained commercial hydroalcoholic extract had small effect on diabetes biomarkers in type-II diabetics.^[81]

Aerial parts 96% aqueous ethanolic extract had **anticancer** activity since it decreased the survival of C118 cells and neural Neurospheres. The effect was also confirmed by antioxidant and anti-inflammatory biomarkers.^[82]

	<p>Roots methanolic (alkaloid) extract had antiparasitic activity against <i>Rhipicephalus</i> (tick) sp. of dog.^[83]</p> <p>Fruits, leaves, roots and stems were separately suspended in water and the filtrates were tested for analgesic and hypothermal activities in barbiturate-induced sleep in mice.^[84]</p> <p>Whole plant DCM extract was chromatographed yielding a new alkaloid Glauvine and <i>O</i>-Methylatheroline (Figure 4A). The structures of the alkaloids were confirmed using spectral methods and chemical modifications.^[85]</p> <p>Whole plant chloroform (alkaloid) extract was analyzed affording, Salutaridine (Figure 4A) Dicentrine and Bulbocapnine.^[86]</p> <p>Follow up of previous study afforded previously presented alkaloids: Allocryptonine, Bulbocapnine, Dicentrine, <i>O</i>-Methylflavinantine, Protopine and Salutaridine.^[87]</p> <p>Leaves chloroform (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Glaucine (major), Isocorydine, Isoboldine and Salutaridine. In this research, the effects of irrigation and salinity were studied.^[88]</p> <p>Analysis of aerial parts DCM (alkaloid) extract afforded Talikmidine (Figure 4B), Isocorydine, Glaucine and Norisocorydine.^[89]</p> <p>Chromatography of aerial parts (from different localities) 95% aqueous ethanolic (alkaloid) extract yielded N-Methylsecoglaucine, Norglaucine (Figure 4B), and Allocryptopine, Dehydroglaucine, Glaucine, Isoboldine, Isocorydine, Protopine and Salutaridine.^[90]</p> <p>Follow up of previous study: analysis of aerial parts (from various localities) DCM (alkaloid) extract was done to compare Glaucine content.^[91]</p> <p>A integrated extraction-pertraction process was developed, and using various solvents, afforded high recovery rates of alkaloids.^[92]</p> <p>Aerial parts 80% aqueous methanolic extract had anticancer activity against HT-29, Caco-2 and T47D cancer cell lines.^[93]</p> <p>Whole plant ethanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding two new alkaloids, Corunnine and Pontevedrine (Figure 4B). These compounds were isolated in small amounts.^[94]</p> <p>Analysis of leaves (from six localities) methanolic extract afforded four well known alkaloids, lipids and phenolics.^[95]</p>
<i>G. grandiflorum</i>	<p>Aerial parts 80% aqueous methanolic extract had antimicrobial activity against three bacterial and three fungal stains.^[39]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was tested for antioxidant activity (ABTS, CUPRAC, βCBM methods) and enzyme inhibition (AChE, BuChE) activity. The extract was chromatographed yielding major components Corydine, Glauciumoline, Isocorydine and Protopine.^[66]</p> <p>Aerial parts 80% aqueous methanolic extract had anticancer activity against HT-29, Caco-2 and T47D cancer cell lines.^[93]</p> <p>Aerial parts methanolic extract has analgesic (hotplate, formalin and rotarod methods) and anti-inflammatory (carrageenan-induced paw edema) activities in rats and mice, respectively. Indomethacin and morphine were reference drugs in this research.^[96]</p> <p>Follow up research of the previous study (analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities): the extract was used to prepare a topical formulation that was tested in rats.^[97]</p> <p>Follow up of the research cited by reference^[96] with acute toxicity test in</p>

rats, that had low effect (797.94 mg/kg).^[98]

Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract that contained high concentrations of Tetrahydroberberine N-oxide, Tetrahydropalmatine (**Figure 5**) and Allocryptopine, had **anti-inflammatory** activity against LPS-induced inflammation in BV2 cells. A mechanism of action is proposed involving ROS inhibition.^[99]

Aerial parts 70% aqueous methanolic extract had was analyzed for TFC and TPC. It was tested for **anti-inflammatory** (COX-2 inhibition method), **antioxidant** (ABTS, DPPH, FRAP, TBARS methods), **AChE inhibition** and **DNA protection** (against hydroxyl radical damages) activities.^[100]

Ethanollic (70% aqueous, ultrasound-assisted, alkaloid) extracts of aerial parts in flowering and fruiting stages, capsules, and roots were prepared and analyzed for total alkaloid content: flowering aerial parts extract was highest. This extract had **anti-inflammatory** activity against formalin-induced paw edema in rats. Indomethacin was reference in this research.^[101]

Aerial parts were separately extracted with chloroform and methanol, and these extracts had **antibacterial** activity against *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus* and *S. sanguis*.^[102]

Aerial parts were separately extracted with ethyl acetate and methanol, and the **antioxidant** activity of these extracts was tested using DPPH, TBARS and superoxide anion scavenging methods.^[103]

Flowering and fruiting aerial parts were extracted with 70% aqueous ethanol. Both extracts were analyzed for TFC and TPC and tested for **antioxidant** activity using DPPH and FRAP methods.^[104]

Leaves methanolic extract was analyzed for GCC, TFC and TPC. It was tested for **antioxidant** activity using ABTS, CUPRAC, DPPH and FRAP methods.^[105]

Whole plant ethanollic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Corypalmine (**Figure 5**) Allocryptopine, Norchelidonine, Protopine, Tetrahydropalmatine, Dihydrochelerythrine and its 8-acetonyl derivative.^[106]

Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed affording Isocorytuberine, N-Methylcanadine (**Figure 5**), and Allocryptopine, Corydine, Isocorydine, and Protopine.^[107]

Aerial parts ethanollic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed yielding Berbithine, Reticuline, Ferulamide (**Figure 5**) and Allocryptopine, N-Methylcanadine and Protopine.^[108]

GCCs of different parts (flowers, fruits, leaves, roots and stems) were separately determined.^[109]

Aerial parts were separately extracted with chloroform, methanol and water, then the extracts were combined, and the alkaloid extract was prepared. The **antioxidant** activity of the extract was tested using the following methods (and references): Fe⁺² chelating (EDTA), DPPH (ascorbic acid), lipid peroxidation with H₂O₂ (BHT), hydroxyl radical scavenging (ascorbic acid) and superoxide anion radical scavenging (ascorbic acid). The **neuroprotective** effect of the extract on PC-12 cells viability was studied in the presence of several neurotoxic chemicals. Effect was measured with oxidant-antioxidant biomarkers. Analysis of the extract showed that the major compounds were Allocryptopine, Tetrahydropalmatine and Tetrahydroberberine N-oxide. A mechanism of action is proposed.^[110]

Aerial parts from different localities were extracted with ethanol and were

	analyzed for alkaloids yielding Allocryptopine, Berbithine, Reticuline, Corydine, Isocorydine, Isocorytuberine, N-Methylcanadine (α and β epimers) and Protopine. The crude extract and alkaloids Corydine, Isocorydine and Protopine were tested for toxicity in brine shrimp showing clear effects (LC_{50} 's). ^[111]
<i>G. leiocarpum</i>	Leaves 90% aqueous ethanolic extract was fractionized with DCM and ethyl acetate. Both fractions were tested for antibacterial activity against three bacteria species, showing weak effect. ^[112] Aerial parts methanolic (alkaloid) extract was chromatographed affording Dehydronorglaucine, Dihydropontevodrine, Lastourvilline, N-Methylcoclaurine, N-Methylglaucine, Predicentrine, Secoglaucine (Figure 6), and Allocryptopine, Glaucine (major component), Oxoglaucine and Protopine. ^[113]

* Unless stated otherwise, percentages of solvent mixtures are V/V.

Figure 1: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium aleppicum*.

Figure 2: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium arabicum*.

Figure 3: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium corniculatum*.

Figure 4A: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium flavum*.

Figure 4B. Natural products isolated from *Glaucium flavum*.

Figure 5: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium grandiflorum*.

Figure 6: Natural products isolated from *Glaucium leiocarpum*.

4. DISCUSSION

In **Table 1** we presented the traditional, ethnobotanical and ethnomedicinal of *Glaucium* wild plants of Israel and Palestine (the RR). One of most special and colourful articles that was published about this topic, which was not included in **Table 1** in order to present its uniqueness, is the work of I. Sezen ahc.^[114] Among several other plant species, *Glaucium grandiflorum* is beautifully presented for its use in urban gardens of Erzurum, Turkey.

But beyond this special article, the major interests of this review article are the medicinal activities of wild *Glaucium* species of the RR and their chemical compositions. These compositions and the active natural products that they include, are highly influenced by growth environments. A.O. Getlawi ahc studied the effect of reduced irrigation (drought) on four *Glaucium* species, of which three are native to the RR.^[115] The main goal of this study was to find the minimal irrigation conditions for these plants cultivation, as part of the efforts to reduce water use in the dry region of the Middle East, with its water crisis. The work focused mainly on morphological changes in the plants. The same group published at the

same time another study that investigated the effect of salinity on these species.^[116] In an earlier publication, J. Cambrollé *et al.* presented the effect of salinity on *Glaucium flavum*, but in addition to morphological parameters, they studied also the effect of chlorophyll content and resulting photosynthesis efficiency and some minerals content.^[117]

In research that was published by A. Elbermawi *et al.*, they reported the isolation of interesting natural products (**Figure 7**) from *Penicillium* sp., an endophyte isolated from *Glaucium arabicum*.^[118] These compounds were tested for several biological activities.

Figure 7: Natural products isolated from *Penicillium* sp., an endophyte isolated from *Glaucium arabicum*.^[118]

In this article it is stated that “*Glaucium arabicum* Fres. (Papaveraceae) is a rare perennial herb endemic to Sinai Peninsula”. This is partially true: this plant is rare, but it is not endemic to Sinai Peninsula. It can be found all over the Middle east: the RR^[119], Jordan^[120] and Saudi Arabia.^[121]

But the growth conditions and environment are only part of the parameters that influence the derived materials from these plants: extractions, oils, decoctions and so on. Consequently, the chemical compositions and the properties-activities are influenced accordingly. F.G. Kocanci *et al.* used the same plant material (*G. corniculatum*) and same solvent (methanol) but used three different extraction methods: Soxhlet, improved Soxhlet and ultrasonication.^[122] There were clear differences in the extract yields, and more important, their chemical compositions, mainly alkaloids and fatty acids. And three years before publication of their study of the

evaluation of Glaucine content in Bulgarian Black Sea Coast localities of *G. flavum*^[91], S. Philipov ahc published a comparative study of alkaloid profile from *G. corniculatum* of Algerian and Bulgarian origin.^[123] They reported very significant differences where the Bulgarian species were much richer. The following alkaloids were detected in the Bulgarian but not in the Algerian plants: Chelitrytryne (Chelerythrine), Corunnine, Isoboldine, Isocorydine, N-Methylaurotetanine, Norglaucine and Sanguinarine. Only Berbitine (**Figure 8**) was detected in the Algerian and not in the Bulgarian plants. Structure according to M. Rahimizadeh.^[124]

Figure 8: Berbitine (Berbithine) isolated from Algerian *Glaucium corniculatum*.^[123]

Another notable differences were found by D.S. Adamovic ahc in the chemical compositions of *Glaucium flavum* in different growth stages: first, second and third year.^[125] Even though findings were not presented properly (table), it is still clear that the differences in alkaloid and some minerals concentrations are clear.

Compared with the genera of *Fumaria* and *Papaver*^[126,127], there was limited use of *Glaucium* species of the RR for preparation of nanoparticles. A.R. Allafchian ahc prepared silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using aerial parts aqueous extract of *G. corniculatum*.^[128] These NPs had antibacterial activity. F. Dehghani ahc used leaves aqueous extract of *G. flavum* to synthesize gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), which had antioxidant and antiviral activities.^[129]

According to several publications, including Y. Abu-Ghalyun ahc^[58] and B. Bozkurt ahc^[65], the major alkaloids of *Glaucium* species are Allocryptopine, Glaucine and Protopine (**Figures 1 and 3**). So, the last part of this section will elaborate on some of their important properties.

Allocryptopine was first isolated by German chemist F. Selle back in 1890^[130], and its epimers were first described by E. Brochmann-Hanssen and B. Nietsen in 1966, along with its biosynthesis.^[131] Not long after, its pharmacological importance and high potency were

recognized and as a result, several review articles were published about it. Among the notable publications, J. Vacek *ahc*^[132] and J. Li *ahc*^[133] One of the most important biological properties of Allocryptopine is its anti-inflammatory activity that was published in several articles like Y. Yang *ahc*^[134], and S. Nigdelioglu Dolanbay *ahc*^[135] In both publications mechanisms of action are proposed. B. Xu *ahc* reported the cardioprotective effect of Allocryptopine in mice cardiomyocytes treated with Isoproterenol.^[136]

Many publications jointly reported the activities of Allocryptopine and Protopine. In a very detailed and comprehensive study, Y-J. Huang *ahc* reported the biotransformation of these compounds in rats.^[137] They discovered that each one of these compounds yields ten metabolites, where some of them have direct effect on liver enzymes. A. Marciniak *ahc* carried out experimental and theoretical study (molecular docking) on the interactions of these compounds with plasma proteins^[138], and they uncovered many similarities in binding modes and pharmacokinetics. W. Hu *ahc* investigated the toxicity of *Macleaya cordata* in mice and their autopsy findings indicate that Protopine caused major toxicity, but the presence of Allocryptopine slightly increased this toxicity.^[139]

To the best of our literature search, Glaucine is the most studied and published of the discussed three compounds, Allocryptopine, Glaucine and Protopine. Despite this, review articles were published about Allocryptopine and Protopine, but not about Glaucine. Glaucine was published for a wide variety of medicinal activities, and we will present here some very selected ones. R. Pons *ahc* reported that inhaling Glaucine had antiasthmatic effect in sensitized guinea pigs.^[140] A year earlier, J. Cortijo *ahc* from the same research group, reported the *in vitro* bronchodilator and anti-inflammatory activities in enzymes isolated from human respiratory system.^[141] And in this context, an interesting study was published by P. Dierckx *ahc* where they compared the cough suppression effects of Glaucine and Codeine in hospitalized patients with chronic cough and reported no differences.^[142] A. Vasquez-Espinal *ahc* conducted a theoretical study (DFT, density functional theory) that showed that Glaucine can react as active antioxidant in certain pH range.^[143] In addition to its antitussive activity, K.H. Ruhle *ahc* reported hypotensive activity^[144], and this activity was also reported by M. Dolores Ivorra *ahc* eight years later^[145] And to complete this part, it is worth mentioning that L. Chang *ahc* investigated the biosynthesis of Glaucine in *Glaucium flavum* and discovered that six enzymes of the type *O*-Methyltransferase are involved.^[146]

In the last three decades, Glaucine is used as a “hidden component” in “legal highs” which are psychoactive preparations, according to B. Geppert *ahc* from Poland.^[147] By extraction and GC-MS analysis, they proved that the concentrations of Glaucine in these preparations exceeded therapeutic doses. P.I. Dargan *ahc* reported Glaucine poisoning in 22 years-old woman who ingested two tablets of “Head Candy”, which is also a “legal high”. Glaucine was extracted and detected by GC-MS.^[148] G.M. Meyer *ahc* reported that Glaucine is used as recreational drug, alone or as part of herbal preparations.^[149] They conducted a detailed and comprehensive research of detection of Glaucine and its metabolites (47, some are toxic) in rat urine. However, a detailed review of the adverse effects of Glaucine on CNS was published by V.I. Rovinskii.^[150]

Scanning the relevant literature reveal the fact that Protopine is the most active and the most published of these three alkaloids, and it was reviewed several times, where the most important review article was published by W. Huang *ahc*.^[151] Among the medicinal properties of Protopine, anti-inflammatory activity is the most published: D.S. Bae *ahc* against LPS-induced in murine macrophages.^[152], Z. Dong *ahc* against carrageenan- and xylene-induced edema in rats^[153] and S.A. Saeed *ahc* against carrageenan-induced edema in rats, against arachidonic acid-induced and inhibition of thromboxane synthesis, *in vitro*.^[154]

But Protopine was published for many more activities: anticancer, C-H. Chun *ahc* against prostate cancer cell lines^[155] and K. Bougoffa-Sadaoui *ahc* against lung cancer cell lines^[156]; L. Ustunes *ahc*, anticholinergic (acetylcholine) and antihistaminic (histamine) in ileum strips from Guinea pigs^[157]; Y. Prokopenko *ahc*, anticonvulsant against Pentylentetrazole-induced seizures in mice^[158]; L-F. Xu *ahc*, antidepressant against 5-hydroxy-tryptophan-induced head twitch response and tail suspension test in mice^[159]; K-O. Hiller *ahc*, antispasmodic and relaxant against Barium chloride-induced seizures in Guinea pig isolated ileum^[160] and; K.H. Janbaz *ahc*, hepatoprotective against Paracetamol- and Carbon tetrachloride-induced hepatotoxicity in rats.^[161]

5. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) *Glaucium* plants of Israel and Palestine possess many biological properties-activities.
- 2) Some of these species were notably studied and published while others were not.
- 3) These plant contain great diversity of alkaloids that were partially studied for activities.
- 4) Research effort is needed to investigate some species and some of their components.
- 5) It is highly important to test and publish adverse effect of the plants and their components.

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